

THE STUDY OF THE PHARMACEUTICAL BUSINESS AND ITS ORGANIZATION IN AZERBAIJAN

**Shiraliyev B.,
Valiyeva M.**

*«Zeytun Pharmaceuticals» LLC
Azerbaijan Medical University*

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Abstract

For the first time in the scientific article, a systematic analysis aimed at the organization and formation of the pharmaceutical business in our country was carried out with analytical-methodological analysis. It has been shown that in the optimization of services in the pharmaceutical market, in order to realize the demand and wishes of consumers, it is necessary to pay attention to the economic balance, taking into account the offers of wholesale and retail sellers-entrepreneurs of pharmaceutical products and the unified price policy adopted in our country. In order to improve pharmaceutical activity in our country, we need to adjust the price of pharmaceutical products to the capabilities of the consumer. In order to fulfill this task, we should pay attention to the basis of the pharmaceutical business in our science-based country and their factors: structure, conjuncture, and chemistry. Also, based on the nomenclature of modern pharmaceutical products, a new competitive marketing strategy should be developed in our country.

Keywords: pharmaceutical business in Azerbaijan.

Relevance. Protecting the health of the population of our country is the most important task of the health authorities. For its successful resolution, it is necessary to improve medicines care for the population in order to prevent and treat various diseases.

The organization of medicines assistance to the population of the Azerbaijan Republic is the most important strategic component of our state. The pharmaceutical market is a socio-economic system for the exchange of pharmaceutical goods and services. In fact, the pharmaceutical market is a developed platform with a high level of competition. Therefore, studying the basics of the pharmaceutical business and its organization in a particular country is extremely important and **relevant**.

The pharmaceutical business is the process of implementing pharmaceutical assistance - an activity aimed at meeting the needs and requirements of the population in pharmaceutical products. The main **goal** of the pharmaceutical business is to optimize the pharmaceutical care market, which is understood as an analysis of the relationship between need, demand and supply, as well as taking into account the influence of all internal factors of the medicine supply system for the population. In other words, the pharmaceutical business implies an analysis of the relationship between demand and supply, as well as an assessment of the influence of all internal factors of the system on the provision of medical services and goods to the population. At the same time, the activities of the pharmaceutical business are not limited to the sale of pharmaceutical products. *Any pharmaceutical product, service, or idea that aims to provide medical care can be the subject of a pharmaceutical business.*

Discussion of the studied material:

The pharmaceutical market consists of many connections and elements, one of which is the pharmaceutical business. Among the factors influencing the func-

tioning of the pharmaceutical market and, consequently, the pharmaceutical business, the following should be highlighted:

1. Geographical (location, climate, proximity to major trade routes);
2. Economic (the level of provision of the region with resources and its general development, scientific and technical capabilities);
3. Political (effectiveness of interaction between different branches and levels of government);
4. Socio-demographic (standard of living of the population);
5. Financial (level of development of the regional banking system);
6. Infrastructural (availability and level of development of infrastructure in the region).

The structure and conjuncture of the pharmaceutical business in Azerbaijan consists of:

1. Analysis of the pharmaceutical market;
2. Analysis of the needs of the pharmaceutical market and forecasting its development;
3. Development of strategic planning methods;
4. Development of integrated methods for generating demand for goods and services of a pharmaceutical profile;
5. Methods for promoting pharmaceutical products in the pharmaceutical market of Azerbaijan;
6. Principle in brand planning and management.

The study of the pharmaceutical business is impossible without defining the key concepts that make up its basis: need, demand, product, exchange, transaction, market for drawing up a business plan for any type of pharmaceutical activity. The pharmaceutical market of Azerbaijan is an important sector of the country's economy, which requires a responsible approach to work, especially in the field of marketing. Pharmaceutical marketing must combine sales promotion with the

obligatory observance of the rules for providing accurate information about services and medicines. We present criteria for pharmaceutical marketing:

1. Carrying out of marketing researches and collection of marketing information ;
2. Planning the range of medicines ;
3. Development of a pricing policy for goods ;
4. Realization, distribution and promotion of goods ;
5. Advertising and sales promotion .

Tasks of pharmaceutical marketing: The functions of pharmaceutical marketing form its tasks:

1. Increasing customer satisfaction;
2. Formation of a permanent consumer audience;
3. Constant market research;
4. Development of a marketing strategy and its implementation;
5. Identification of demand and unmet needs;
6. Forecasting the need for goods;
7. Development of measures to improve the organization of production;
8. Assessment of the competitiveness of manufactured products.

Depending on the size and specifics of a pharmaceutical enterprise, the following marketing models of a particular unit can be presented: functional, product, regional, segment, combined.

Currently, the following types of pharmaceutical marketing are relevant: conversion marketing, incentive marketing, developing marketing, remarketing, synchromarketing, supportive marketing, counter marketing, behavioral marketing, innovative marketing, integrated marketing, direct marketing, strategic marketing, target marketing.

The legal basis of a particular country is the most important condition for organizing a pharmaceutical business. At present, many countries of the world, including the Republic of Azerbaijan, have adopted the required legislative and regulatory documents regulating the behavior of entities in the pharmaceutical market, adopted during 1992-2022. (The Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, laws on entrepreneurship, pharmaceutical activities, medicines, licensing, registration of medicines, etc.). Since gaining its independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan has been constantly improving its regulatory and legislative framework, including in the field of pharmaceuticals (1-15), a number of laws regulating pharmaceutical activities have been adopted. In order to improve the pharmaceutical business in our country, a perfect regulatory and legal framework has been created (16-17).

Revealing the organizational component of the pharmaceutical business, we first of all studied the pharmaceutical products necessary for the pharmaceutical business, which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Name of pharmaceutical products.

No.	Name	Description
1.	Full name (FN)	The official name of the medicine, containing the parameters necessary for its identification (for example: dosage form, dosage, release form, etc.)
2.	Trade name (TN)	Official trade name
3.	Pharm. Group	Classification of the medicine depending on its pharmacological action
4.	Brand	Generalized TN
5.	Manufacturer	Registration certificate owner
6.	Country	RC owner country
7.	ATC	Anatomical- therapeutic -chemical classification according to WHO (http://www.whocc.no/atcddd)
8.	Dietary supplements	Classification of Dietary supplements
9.	Cosmetics	AM classification - anatomical and morphological classification
		Age groups, classification
		Indications for the use of medical cosmetics, classification
		The action of a cosmetic product, classification
10.	EPhMRA	Classification on version of the European Pharmaceutical Marketing Research Association (http://www.ephmra.org)
11.	INN	International non-proprietary name
12.	Dosage form	Dosage form is a convenient for use condition given to a medicinal product or medicinal plant material, in which the desired therapeutic effect is achieved.
13.	Product type	OTC medicines, dietary supplements, medical cosmetics, etc.
14.	Region	Regional unit
15.	Volume, [RUB / USD / EUR].	Sales value
16.	Natural volumes	Sales volumes in physical terms
17.	Volume, pac.	Volume expressed in the number of medicine packages
18.	Volume in "tablets"	Volume, expressed in the number of dosage forms of medicines (for example, tablets, etc.)

No.	Name	Description
19.	Volume in daily doses	DDDs - volume in daily doses. DDDs = amount of medicine/DDD, where the amount of the medicine = dosage * number of Medicine Form in the package * number of packages sold Defined Daily Dose (DDD) - (standard daily dose) - determines the average maintenance daily dose of a medicine used for its main purpose in adults. http://www.whooc.no/atcddd)
20.	Volume in mega units of insulin	Volume of insulin preparations in International Insulin Mega Units (IU): Number of packages x number of international units in 1 package / 1000000
21.	Purchase price	
	<i>arithmetic mean, [AZN / RUB / USD / EUR]</i>	
	<i>weighted average, [AZN / RUB / USD / EUR]</i>	
	<i>minimum, [AZN / RUB / USD / EUR]</i>	
	<i>maximum, [AZN / RUB / USD / EUR]</i>	
22.	Sale, weighted average price, [AZN / RUB / USD / EUR]	
23.	Confidence interval upper limit, [AZN / RUB / USD / EUR]	
24.	Confidence interval lower limit, [AZN / RUB / USD / EUR]	
25.	Average price in the region, [AZN / RUB / USD / EUR]	
26.	Representation	
27.	OTC/RX	A sign that the medicine belongs to OTC or prescription medicines [2]
28.	VED	A sign that a medicine belongs to the list of the List of Vital and Essential Medicines and Medical Devices
29.	Domestic	Sign of belonging of the medicine to the medicines of domestic production
30.	Branded generic	Branded A generic is a generic medicine that is on the market under a new original (proprietary) name.
31.	Original	An original medicine is a first synthesized or modified previously known substance that has passed a full cycle of preclinical and clinical studies, a medicine that represents an undoubted step forward in any pharmacotherapeutic group. and other research. The medicine remains original even after the end of patent protection.
32.	Unbranded generic	Unbranded generic is a generic medicine that is marketed under a common generic name. These include medicines whose generic name is the same as the trade name, or whose trade name is widely used and “generally accepted” for this INN (for example, “analgin” for metamizole sodium) and is produced by several manufacturers.

The next stage in the development of the pharmaceutical business in our country is the organization of wholesale and retail pharmaceutical organizations with

an approved assortment medicine policy, both in quantitative and qualitative aspects (13-1 6).

Typically, the structure of modern pharmaceutical products used is divided as follows:

We have developed a recommendatory strategy for the competitive selection of a segment of the pharmaceutical market in Azerbaijan, presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Marketing strategy for the competitiveness of the choice of the pharmaceutical market of the Azerbaijan Republic.

For the first time, we studied the methodological basis of the pharmaceutical business and its organization, and also carried out an analytical processing of the marketing strategy, which is necessary to identify the competitiveness of the country's pharmaceutical market.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A systematic analysis was carried out for the organization of the pharmaceutical business in our country, the factors were studied: structure, conjuncture, the main key criteria for its formation.

2. A methodology for organizing pharmaceutical marketing for pharmaceutical products has been developed: a modern list of required pharmaceutical products is presented.

3. For the first time, a marketing strategy has been developed for the competitiveness of the choice of the pharmaceutical market in our country, which is very necessary for organizing a private pharmaceutical business.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku, 11/12/1995
2. "Tax Code" of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku, 2003
3. "Labor Code" of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku, 2003
4. Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Accounting". Baku, 1995
5. Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Protection of Population's Health". Baku, 01/17/1997
6. Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Medicines". Baku, 2007
7. Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan "Regulation on granting special consent

(license) to certain types of entrepreneurial activity". Baku, 1997

8. Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "State program on the privatization of state property in the Republic of Azerbaijan during 1995-1998", Baku, 1995

9. Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Standardization". Baku, 1996

10. Order No. 172 of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan "Rules for issuing medicines from pharmacy organizations", Baku, 2010

11. Order No. 153 of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan on "Requirements for the establishment and operation of pharmacy organizations". Baku, 02.10.2006.

12. "Rules for State Registration and Registry of Medicines". Resolution No. 108 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated July 13, 2007.

13. 3 to "Rules for state registration and registry of medicinal products"; four; 5; Attachments No. 6. Resolution No. 108 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated July 13, 2007.

14. Rules for conducting pharmacological and toxicological tests and reports of medicinal products during the examination of registration materials. Order of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

15. Rules for conducting additional tests on bioavailability and equivalence of medicinal products during the examination of registration materials. Order of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

16. M. Valiyeva, A. Abdullazade, P. Azizbeyov. To pharmaceutical activity in the country organization of control /Azerbaijan Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacotherapy, 2012, No. 1, pp. 33-38.

17. M. Valiyeva, Sh. Jabbarova. Management and economics of pharmacy, pp. 10-13, 18-24, 30-35, Baku 2013.

18. M.N.Velieva "Organization of the pharmaceutical service in Azerbaijan" Modern pharmacy: problems and development prospects. Materials of the V Interregional scientific and practical conference with international participation May 29-30, 2015, Vladikavkaz, 2015, p.303-306

19. M.N. Veliyeva, F.A. Ismailova "To improve management methods in the pharmaceutical market of

Azerbaijan" Public health and health care. Volume IV, Baku, 2016, p. 28 4-285

20. M.N. Velieva, S.A. Atakishchizade "Development of methodological approaches to innovative activities of pharmaceutical enterprises in Azerbaijan" Development, research and marketing of new pharmaceutical products. Collection scientific works. Issue 71, Pyatigorsk, 2016, p.96-97

CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO UNDERSTANDING STAFF SATISFACTION IN ORGANIZATIONS: INTERNATIONAL THEORIES

Samadov S..

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Teacher of the department "Management", phd.

Sheydai T..

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Employee of the department "Management"

Safarli Z.

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Employee of the department "Management"

КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ПОНИМАНИЮ УДОВЛЕТВОРЕННОСТИ СОТРУДНИКОВ В ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ ТЕОРИИ

Самедов С.М.

Азербайджанский Государственный Университет Нефти и Промышленности, Преподаватель кафедры "Менеджмент", д. ф. э.

Шейдан Т.А.

Азербайджанский Государственный Университет Нефти и Промышленности, Сотрудник кафедры "Менеджмент"

Сафарли З.Х.

Азербайджанский Государственный Университет Нефти и Промышленности, Сотрудник кафедры "Менеджмент"
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Abstract

In the era of rapidly evolving technology and competitive environment, the greatest value needed for organizations to survive is undoubtedly their existing workforce. All organizations aiming at success in both public and private sectors should focus on research and development and human resources.

The main objective of this study is to determine the level of employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment, to identify the relationship between them, as well as to investigate the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

The article emphasizes the concept of job satisfaction, its importance, and the accepted theories regarding job satisfaction. Factors affecting job satisfaction and the impact of job satisfaction on work life were discussed.

Аннотация

В настоящее время, быстро развивающейся технологии и конкурентной среды, необходимой для выживания наибольшую ценность для организации, конечно, существующей рабочей силы. Все организации, стремящиеся добиться успеха в государственном и частном секторах, должны сосредоточиться на исследованиях и разработках, а также на людских ресурсах.

Основная цель этого исследования - определить уровень удовлетворенности сотрудников и организационную принадлежность, выявить связи между ними и изучить взаимосвязь между удовлетворенностью работой и организационной принадлежностью.

В статье подчеркивается концепция удовлетворенности работой, ее важность и принятые теории удовлетворенности работой.

Обсуждались факторы, влияющие на удовлетворенность работой и влияние удовлетворенности работой на трудовую жизнь.

Keywords: employee satisfaction, motivation, hierarchy of needs, two-factor theory, expectations theory

Ключевые слова: удовлетворенность работников, мотивация, иерархия потребностей, двухфакторная теория, теория ожиданий